

Kinetic and equilibrium study of chromium(VI) sorption on vermicompost

O. P. Bansal

Chemistry Department, D. S. College, Aligarh-202 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : drop1955@gmail.com

Manuscript received 30 December 2010, revised 06 May 2011, accepted 17 August 2011

Abstract : The study concerns with the adsorption of Cr^{VI} under varying pH, contact time and also the effect of concentration of Cr^{VI} on vermicompost. The optimum pH and time of contact required for maximum adsorption was found to be 4 and 180 min respectively and adsorption decreased as pH rises above 4. Freundlich adsorption model was best fit for the adsorption data. The values of $1/n$ were less than unity implying a strong interaction between sorbent and metal ions. The kinetics of adsorption was found to follow the first order reversible reaction. The desorption rate constant was smaller than adsorption rate constant indicating a stable metal sorbent complex. The standard enthalpy changes (ΔH°) showed the process is exothermic; the values of ΔG° support the inference that sorption process is spontaneous.

Keywords : Vermicompost, chromium, first order reversible reaction, thermodynamics parameters, isotherms.

Introduction

Heavy metals are important environmental pollutants threatening the health of human population and native ecosystem. In agricultural soils, the heavy metals which depress the growth of plants¹ are introduced mainly by application of fertilizers, living materials, sewage sludge composts and other industrial and urban waste materials^{2,3}. The agriculturists are much worried about this pollution, especially the entry of toxic elements into the food chain. The indiscriminate and continuous use of raw sewage water and industrial waste water for irrigation has elevated the levels of available heavy metals in the cultivated layer of soils⁴ as well as in vegetables and fodder crops grown in such soils⁵. Ingestion and accumulation of toxic metals in the human beings causes toxic effects like inhibition of haemoglobin formation, sterility, hypertension, kidney damage and mental retardation⁶. The accumulation of chromium in urban soils via wastewaters of electroplating, dye, cement and paint industries has received significant attention in developing countries⁷. Cr^{VI} is reported to be powerful carcinogen capable of modifying the DNA transcription process in both animals and humans that may result in important chromosome aberrations.

As the sewage-effluent of Aligarh district contains higher concentration of chromium due to small scale in-

dustries like electroplating, paints, it was considered useful to assess the effect of various parameters viz. contact time, pH, temperature and concentration on the sorption of Cr^{VI} on the vermicompost using equilibrium adsorption, kinetics and thermodynamic models.

Results and discussion

Effect of contact time :

The adsorption of Cr^{VI} by vermicompost increased with increasing of contact time (Fig. 1). Above 50% of Cr^{VI} adsorption occurred in the first 30 min and thereafter the rate of adsorption of Cr^{VI} on vermicompost became slow, and the rate of adsorption became very slow

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on Cr^{VI} adsorption on vermicompost.

after 180 min. The slow adsorption after 90 min probably is due to the electrostatic hindrance between adsorbed negatively charged sorbate species on the surface of adsorbent and the slow pore diffusion of the solute ion into the bulk of the adsorbent⁸. The results also suggest that during Cr^{VI} adsorption on vermicompost the pore diffusion is the rate limiting step.

Effect of pH :

Adsorption of Cr^{VI} on vermicompost increased with pH upto pH 4 and thereafter it decreased. As in strongly acidic solution the hydroxyl groups exposed on the periphery of the vermicompost surface are protonated and acquire a positive charge. These protonated sites are then available for the interaction and adsorption of Cr^{VI} ions present in solution⁹. With the increase in pH the protonated sites diminishes with decrease in adsorption. The decrease in adsorption from pH 4 to 6 was 40%.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on Cr^{VI} adsorption on vermicompost.

Equilibrium studies :

The results of this study showed that adsorption equilibrium of Cr^{VI} on vermicompost at all the studied temperatures followed the Freundlich isotherm ($R^2 = 0.95-0.97$) (Fig. 3). The logarithmic form of equation often used to fit batch equilibrium data is, $\ln Q_e = \ln K_F + 1/n \ln C_e$, where K_F (mg/g) and $1/n$ indicate adsorption capacity and adsorption intensity respectively. The linear plot of $\ln Q_e$ vs $\ln C_e$ gives slope of value of $1/n$ and an intercept $\ln K_F$. The values of $1/n$ and K_F are given in Table 2. The small values of $1/n$ imply a strong interaction between sorbent and metal ions⁸. The values of $1/n$ increased while of K_F decreased with increase in temperature denoting that with rise in temperature sorption

Table 1. Characteristics of air dried vermicompost

Characteristics	
pH (1 : 5)	7.3
Organic matter (% w/w)	39.6
Nitrogen (% w/w)	2.02
C/N ratio	11.26
Clay (% w/w)	47
Silt (% w/w)	16
Sand (% w/w)	37
Total metal (mg kg ⁻¹)	
Al	15200
Fe	18700
Ca	6035
Mg	2360
Pb	2.2
Cd	1.8
Cu	28.4
Ni	16.4
Zn	84
Cr	4.6

Fig. 3. Adsorption isotherms of Cr adsorption on vermicompost at different temperatures.

Table 2. Freundlich isotherm constants for Cr^{VI} adsorption on vermicompost

Parameter	Temperature (K)		
	293	303	313
$1/n$	0.65	0.67	0.70
K_F (mg g ⁻¹)	5.69	4.73	4.04

of metal ions on vermicompost surface decreases.

Adsorption kinetics :

Adsorption of Cr^{VI} on vermicompost followed first

Table 3. Calculated k_1 , k_2 and thermodynamic parameters for Cr^{VI} adsorption on vermicompost

Temp. (K)	$C_0 = 10 \text{ mg/L}$					
	X_e	k_1 (min^{-1})	k_2 (min^{-1})	ΔG° (kJ/mol)	ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J/mol K)
293	0.85	0.0423	0.00747	-4.23		
303	0.76	0.0302	0.00954	-2.86	-16.66	-44.8
313	0.675	0.0246	0.0118	-1.90		

order reversible reaction, the integral form for the model⁷

is $-\ln \left(\frac{C_A - C_e}{C_0 - C_e} \right) = (k_1 + k_2) t$, where k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants for adsorption and desorption, C_e (mg/L) equilibrium concentration, C_0 (mg/L) = initial concentration and C_A (mg/L) = concentration after time t . The plot between $[-\ln (C_A - C_e)/(C_0 - C_e)]$ vs t is a straight line with slope $(k_1 + k_2)$. The constants k_1 and k_2 are related to sorbate concentration as $k_1/k_2 = X_e/(1 - X_e) = (C_0 - C_e)/C_e$, X_e = fraction adsorption at equilibrium. The results are given in Table 3, the data of Table 3 indicate that the rate constant for the forward reaction is higher than backward reaction (desorption). The low values of k_2 indicate that adsorbed chromium is relatively stable on the adsorbent.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The thermodynamic parameters i.e. ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated using following equations.

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K; \ln (K_2/K_1) = -\Delta H^\circ/R (1/T_2 - 1/T_1);$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$$

The values are given in Table 3. The negative values of ΔH° denote that sorption of Cr^{VI} on vermicompost is exothermic. The values of ΔG° were also negative and decreased with temperature indicating that sorption is less favoured at high temperature. Negative values of ΔS° showed that there is no configuration change and that complex of sorption of Cr on vermicompost surface is stable. Association, fixation or immobilization of the Cr^{VI} ions as a result of adsorption resulted in the loss of degrees of freedom of the adsorbate ions, producing negative entropy effects.

Regeneration study :

The results of the regeneration study are shown in Table 4. The results showed that removal of Cr^{VI} was ~40% and adsorption capacity did not decrease appreciably and vermicompost can be used to remove Cr^{VI} .

Table 4. Equilibrium adsorption capacity of Cr^{VI} by vermicompost

Regeneration no.	Initial concentration (mg/L)	Equilibrium Cr^{VI} removal %
I	10	41.50
II	10	40.69
III	10	41.03

Conclusions :

(i) Contact time required for the maximum adsorption is 90 min.

(ii) Optimum pH for maximum adsorption of Cr^{VI} is 4.

(iii) Equilibrium data fitted to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

(iv) Adsorption process followed first order reversible reaction.

(v) Standard free energy change (ΔG°) and standard enthalpy change (ΔH°) indicate that adsorption process is spontaneous and exothermic.

Experimental

A commercial sample of manure vermicompost which was produced in vermicompost department was used as adsorbing material. The vermicompost properties are given in Table 1.

The effect of contact time on equilibrium for the adsorption/removal of Cr by vermicompost was carried out by taking 1 g vermicompost and adding 250 mL of Cr^{VI} solution of concentration 10 and 20 mg L^{-1} in a 500 mL flask. The stock solution of Cr^{VI} with 500 mg L^{-1} was prepared by dissolving $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in deionised water in volumetric flask. This solution was then diluted to obtain standard solution of 10 and 20 mg L^{-1} . The samples were continuously shaken for various time periods ranging from 10 min to 24 h, and then centrifuged and the Cr in super-

natant solution was analysed by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. To check the reproducibility of the experimental data, each experiment was conducted thrice. The amount of Cr adsorbed on the adsorbent was calculated as : $q = \frac{(CA_0 - CA)V}{W}$, where CA_0 and CA are the Cr^{VI} concentration (mg/L) in solution initially and at any time t respectively. V is the volume taken in flask and W is the weight of adsorbent used. The results are given in Fig. 1.

The effects of the equilibrium pH on adsorption was investigated at pH values ranging from 2 to 12 and were obtained by adding 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH as per requirement. 1 g of vermicompost and 250 ml of Cr^{VI} solution (final concentration 20 mg/L) were shaken in 500 ml flask for 12 h, followed by centrifugation. The amount of Cr^{VI} adsorbed/removed was calculated as above. The results are given in Fig. 2.

The equilibrium study was carried out by shaking 1 g of vermicompost with various amounts of Cr^{VI} (0–50 mg of Cr^{VI}) at a constant volume of 250 mL in a 500 mL flask for 12 h, at three temperatures 293 ± 1 ; 303 ± 1 and 313 ± 1 K. After centrifugation the Cr^{VI} was analyzed and amount adsorbed was calculated as above. The results of adsorption are recorded in Fig. 3. The percentage of Cr^{VI} removed was calculated as % removal

$$= \frac{(CA_0 - CA)}{CA_0}.$$

For the regeneration study, 1 g of the adsorbent used in the equilibrium study was regenerated for 2 h by contacting with 250 mL of 1 M NaCl solution in 500 ml of flask. This experiment was repeated thrice with fresh solution. Finally the adsorbent was washed with deionised water to remove all the free chloride ions.

References

1. P. K. Chhonkar, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 2004, **52**, 357.
2. J. Y. Dai, M. Q. Xy, J. P. Chen, X. P. Yand and Z. S. Ko, *Chemosphere*, 2007, **66**, 353.
3. N. Asagai, H. Veno and A. Ebid, *Int. J. Soil Sci.*, 2007, **2**, 171.
4. G. S. Dheri, M. S. Brar and S. S. Malhi, *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 2007, **38**, 1353.
5. M. J. Mohammad Rusan, S. Hinnawi and L. Rousan, *Desalination*, 2007, **215**, 143.
6. M. O. Amdur, J. Doulland and C. D. Classen, "Toxicology. The Basic Science of Poisons", Pergamon Press, New York, 1991, pp. 639-641.
7. U. C. Ghosh and S. Goswami, *Water S.A.*, 2005, **31**, 597.
8. F. Jonethan, A. N. Kosasih, J. Sunarso, Y-Hsu. Jua, N. Indraswati and S. Ismadri, *J. Hazard Material*, 2009, **162**, 616.
9. K. K. Singh, R. Rastogi and S. H. Hasan, *J. Coll. Int. Sci.*, 2005, **290**, 61.